

CST4ALL

Support to the Activities of the Concentrated Solar Thermal Technology Area of the SET Plan

CST4ALL Industry Workshop on the hybridisation of Concentrated Solar Thermal Technologies (CST) with biomass

Date	7 May 2024
Time	09:00 – 12:00 CEST
Online event	Microsoft Teams
Registration link	Available here

Agenda

09:00	Welcome and introduction to CST4ALL project and webinar objectives Konstantinos Genikomsakis – <i>ESTELA</i>
09:10	Message from the European Commission Elisabeth Schellmann – <i>DG for Energy, European Commission</i>
09:15	Keynote presentations on hybridisation possibilities of CST and biomass Yuvaraj Sathiyadev Pandian – <i>Solarlite CSP Technology GmbH</i> Morten Tony Hansen – <i>Ea Energy Analyses</i> Poul Vestergaard Jensen – <i>Brønderslev Forsyning A/S</i> Q&A
10:15	Live poll
10:20	Break
10:30	Round table: Industrial maturity of technologies, bankability of projects, R&I contributions, necessary skills and manufacturing facilities in Europe <u>Moderator:</u> Derek Baker – <i>ODTÜ-GÜNAM Center for Solar Energy Research and Applications</i> <u>Participants:</u> Yuvaraj Sathiyadev Pandian – <i>Solarlite CSP Technology GmbH</i> Bernhard Leuenberger – <i>TSK Flagsol Engineering</i>

**Funded by
the European Union**

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	Iñaki Zamora Oyarzun – <i>TSK Energy Solutions</i> María Luisa Revilla Trujillo – <i>Centre for the Development of Industrial Technology (CDTI)</i> Patxi Sorbet – <i>National Renewable Energy Centre (CENER)</i> Patrik Klintbom – <i>ETIP Bioenergy</i> Jean-Marc Jossart – <i>Bioenergy Europe</i> Ruben Bartali – <i>Fondazione Bruno Kessler</i>
11:50	Wrap-up and conclusions Peter Heller – <i>German Aerospace Center (DLR)</i>
12:00	End of workshop

This CST4ALL project event is organised with the support of the European Technology and Innovation Platform Bioenergy (ETIP Bioenergy).

CST4ALL Coordinator

**Deutsches Zentrum
für Luft- und Raumfahrt e.V.**
in der Helmholtz-Gemeinschaft

DLR: Deutsches Zentrum fuer Luft - Und Raumfahrt EV (DE)

CST4ALL Partners

CIEMAT: Centro de Investigaciones Energeticas, Medioambientales y Tecnologicas (ES)

ENEA: Agenzia nazionale per le nuove tecnologie, l'energia e lo sviluppo economico sostenibile (IT)

ESTELA: European Solar Thermal Electricity Association (BE)

GUNAM: Center for Solar Energy Research and Applications (TR)

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